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Effective Pedagogical Technologies for Forming Critical and Creative Thinking in Future Primary Teachers

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Abstract: *This article provides a detailed overview of effective pedagogical techniques for forming critical and creative thinking in primary school students.*

Key words: *research, activity, cooperation, competition, group, thinking, knowledge, skills, competence, self-confidence, formation, support, independent thinking, strategy.*

Introduction. Bloom's Cube Technique. How to develop critical thinking skills in your student? What techniques and technologies should we use? We offer one of the famous methods of critical thinking technology, developed by the American scientist and psychologist Benjamin Bloom. This method is called Bloom's Cube. Benjamin Bloom is known as the author of a unique system of algorithms for pedagogical activity. The theory or "taxonomy" he proposes divides learning objectives into five blocks: cognitive, psychomotor, and affective. Simply put, these objectives can be identified by the blocks "I know," "I create," and "I can do." That is, the child is not offered ready-made knowledge, but a problem is presented. And he must use his experience and knowledge to find ways to solve this problem.

Example.

Topic: "ANIMAL VARIETY"

(Natural Sciences, Grade 2)

Name.

1. Name all the vertebrate and invertebrate animals you know.
2. Name both vertebrate and invertebrate animals that you have seen.
3. Name both vertebrate and invertebrate animals in our area.

Why?

4. Why do we call them “invertebrates and invertebrates”?
5. Why is a spider’s body covered with a hard shell?
6. Why are vertebrates and invertebrates different from each other?

Think.

7. Think about the similarities between wasps and bees.
8. Think about how bees differ from wasps.
9. Think about the importance of bees in nature.
10. Think about how bees benefit trees.

Suggestion.

11. Suggest how knowing about jellyfish would benefit you.
12. Suggest how humans can help jellyfish survive in a changing environment.

Explanation.

13. How do jellyfish breathe through their skin or is this not true?
14. Do you think jellyfish are an important part of the ecosystem?

Share.

- ✓ Share with others how frogs make you feel.
- ✓ How do you feel about frogs?
- ✓ Tell us what was the most interesting and the most boring (unpleasant) part of the lesson.

“True-False” technique. Each participant writes on a piece of paper one correct and one incorrect opinion about the topic being studied or studied. Participants are grouped into pairs, exchange sheets of paper and determine which opinion is incorrect.

Scope of use: can be used when checking homework, to consolidate the topic studied in natural and exact sciences.

Advantages: develops observational and information-selective skills, teaches children to find mistakes and express thoughts, allows teachers to check students' knowledge.

Disadvantages: children who have not mastered the material are at risk of failing the assignment. It is difficult to monitor the clarity and correctness of ideas and allocate time for teaching, because students often do not have the skills to clearly express their thoughts.

Example.

Topic: Forest doctors (Mother tongue and reading literacy, grade 1).

1. If you hear the sound of “taq... taq... taq...” in a place where trees grow thickly, know that there is a redwood tree here.

True / False

2. Red-tailed hawks do not breed in the forests of Uzbekistan.

True / False

3. Red-tailed hawks only live in trees, they do not fly.

True / False

4. Red-tailed hawks build nests in tree hollows.

True / False

5. The largest red-tailed hawk in the world lives in America.

True / False 6. Red-tailed hawks build nests in the hollows of plants.

True / False 7. A mother red-breasted hen lays 2 to 12 eggs.

True / False 8. There are more than 220 species of hens in the world.

True / False

Discussion. The method of “thick” and “thin” questions. When using questions in the educational process, it is customary to divide them into two types: simple and complex questions. Simple questions are those that can be answered with "yes" or "no" or other single words. They can also be called short or complex questions, if you put them in a short or complex way. Complex questions are those that require a response with several words, phrases, sentences, or a relevant explanation. They can also be called thick questions, if they are presented in a complete or incomplete form. Therefore, the name of this method of “thick” and “thin” questions can also be called the method of “full” and “short” or “complete” and “short” questions. This method can be used at various stages of the lesson to quickly monitor the learning of students and increase their activity. To do this, the teacher should prepare a table of "bold" and "thin" questions related to the topic of the lesson in advance.

Sample.

Topic: LIVE SHOPPING (Education, Grade 2)..

"Subtle" questions	"Tough" questions
Why couldn't the butterfly help the chick?	What do you think about the story "The Living Basket"?
Why couldn't Shumshuq help the chick?	What would you do if you were Joja?
Why didn't your friend's advice help?	How would you help the chick?
How did Shumoli help the chick?	Who is the main character in the fairy tale? Why?
Who kept banging their beak on the egg?	What do you understand by the words "unity, unity, truth, and abundance"?

The game “Plus and Minus”.

The purpose of the game: to identify the social actions of students towards each other, as well as to teach them to think positively and negatively.

How the game works: Each student writes down his or her positive and negative qualities on separate pieces of paper. Then all the pieces of paper are mixed up and placed in the middle of the class. The children sit in a circle, take turns taking a piece of paper, read it silently, and place it in front of the person they think it is written about (with the text upside down). Then everyone reads the paper in front of them. Comments are given as desired.

Example.

Topic: Summer (Mother Language and Reading Literacy, Grade 1).

Each student states 3 positive and 3 negative thoughts on the topic of summer.

POSITIVE:

1. Summer is the hottest season of the year.
2. A lot of fruits ripen during this season.
3. With the arrival of summer, vacations begin and children go to summer camps.

NEGATIVE:

1. In summer, everything gets very hot.
2. Many children are afraid of swimming.
3. The days will be long and the nights short, and it will be very difficult to fall asleep in the morning.

Euler circles. Euler circles are a new type of intersection or union problem that requires finding some intersection or union of sets, given certain conditions. Euler circles are a geometric diagram that can be used to visually represent relationships between small sets. Euler's method is indispensable for solving some problems, and also simplifies thinking. However, before proceeding with the solution of the problem, it is necessary to analyze the situation. Sometimes it is easier to solve the problem using arithmetic operations.

Methodology for developing skills for forming critical and creative thinking based on Bloom's Cube (according to K. Nuraliyeva)

When developing students' creative abilities using the Bloom's Cube technique, the following aspects should be taken into account:

- 1) the technique is appropriate for the consolidation, or reflection, stage of the lesson. Because it helps to understand the personal, practical and social significance of the studied educational materials;
- 2) it is necessary to formulate questions in relation to practical life. Bloom's Cube technique helps to analyze the application of the topic in real life;
- 3) it is considered appropriate to offer students creative exercises before working with the technique. This will encourage students to demonstrate their creative abilities in the process of working with the technique;

4) it is appropriate to present questions and answers in audio and/or multimedia form. Because it is difficult for students to grasp the questions and answers in one hearing.

When working with the Bloom's Cube technique, students can be offered several alternative options:

- 1) having students work in groups to answer the questions;
- 2) asking students to independently formulate questions;
- 3) organizing the work in the format of a board game. To do this, it is necessary to create a standard playground for small groups to walk around with cards with questions;
- 4) It is also effective to use it in integrated lessons.

Also, along with the Bloom's Cup technique, you can use such techniques as mind maps, case studies, four-wheel drive, SMARTER, five "whys?", heuristic research, "thick" and "thin" questions.

Conclusion. In conclusion, in the formation of critical and creative thinking of primary school students, it is necessary to apply the principle of ideality of educational activities. Because the higher the ideality of educational activities, the higher the possibility of forming creative abilities. At the same time, the practical application of pedagogical techniques for the formation of creative abilities is directly related to the level of methodological competence of the teacher. In short, the formation of creative abilities in primary school students expands the opportunity for quality education.

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